

CONCEPT OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES AND ITS ESSENCE

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Annotation: In this article opinions about the importance of multimedia technologies in science and development and the essence of these technologies are presented.

Keywords: Multimedia technologies, educational system, methodology, higher education, information media.

INTRODUCTION.

Talking about the development of music art today and tomorrow, we should pay special attention to the meaning of the phrase "national music". Protecting it from any negative influences, including foreign currents in the spirit of "mass culture", should be one of the main goals of today's music culture teachers. When talking about this, we should emphasize such a situation, because the young generation should understand in the process of education how precious and high their spiritual and cultural values are, the art of national music. . The "works" presented to the public by some young performers and creative groups do not meet any requirements and criteria of art. Not only their music, theme and performance methods, but also their stage actions are openly foreign "pop-art"¹ the fact that there are frequent cases of people suffering from "star disease" by imitating the appearance of celebrities does not fail to offend true art lovers. Such actions of young people who distort words and try to be recognized through various clips are a result of ignorance and lack of understanding of the true essence of art. I don't think it's anything else.

In order to prevent and put an end to such problems, cultural organizations, especially musicologists, master artists, composers, journalists and writers, and a large number of art lovers, express their opinions openly and educate our youth. it is both a debt and a duty to the state and society. For example, if a person's ear gets used to light, shallow tones, as a result, his artistic taste, musical culture and thinking will decrease, his spiritual world will be destroyed. It is not a question of false concepts taking over. As a result, it will be difficult for such a person to accept the unique masterpieces of our national music, such as "Munojot", "Shashmaqom", and the works of great world-renowned composers, such as Beethoven, Mozart, Bach and Tchaikovsky. In order to prevent such situations, it is necessary to create a healthy creative environment among artists, to raise the spiritual world and cultural level of the growing young generation, to create the necessary conditions for our youth to widely enjoy the examples of national and world music culture, and this on the basis of further development of musical education, issues of further improvement of personnel training system in this regard are considered in laws and regulations.

¹ "Pop-art"- (popular art) people's public opposition is that they don't respect people, but rather things and objects. They appreciate the feelings of household consumerism. Wikipedia-2022

In accordance with the decision of the President of February 2, 2022 "On additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art" "... from 2022 measures of state support for the sphere of culture and art" It was decided to introduce competitions to create at least 100 high-art audiovisual works for the Internet and social networks, to process at least 150 of the best national songs for karaoke performance as an introduction to². In order to ensure the implementation of these decisions and decrees, it is necessary to effectively use modern information technologies in the educational process, to form computer literacy, and to provide the first necessary concepts about the Internet. Effective use of information and communication technologies in lessons is of particular importance in increasing the capacity of current personnel and the productivity and efficiency of pedagogues. The demand for multimedia technologies is increasing day by day. This creates the need to develop multimedia tools based on information and communication technologies, including school textbooks, study guides, lesson plans.

Literature review and analysis.

In the "Music" textbooks intended for the school program, all tasks intended for students are given. G. Sharipova, Z. Khodjayeva's "Methodology of Music Teaching" describes the teacher's methods of working with students in the educational process, approaching each subject with new and unique pedagogical technologies. D.A.Karimova, Sh.A.Yakubova in the book "Working on children's musical works" learn how to perform works of various forms and genres, reveal the artistic images of the musical work based on the sheet music, melody, timbre, rhythm, sound, dynamic colors, body movements corresponding to the melody. information is provided. E.K. Djalilov's "School Repertoire" contains educational methods, pedagogical and psychological methodical recommendations for music teachers, opinions and methodical recommendations about new pedagogical technologies. G. M. Sharipova, D. F. Asamova, Z. L. Khodjayeva in the "Methodology of Music Teaching Theory and School Repertoire" workshop, use of modern technologies in the preparation of lesson plans, the ability to use computers, slides, disks, magnetic tapes, methods of teaching music according to the age of each class and we can see that knowledge is given about choosing and applying methods.

If we look at history, we will see that the concept of multimedia has nothing to do with the term computer technology. This concept was first used by English singer Bob Goldstein. In 1966, he used the term "multimedia" during the presentation of his new show. Later, the term came to mean any entertainment product with sound and video. Only at the end of the 1990s, this word began to be defined clearly. By 1988, the concept of multimedia was formed by the European Commission, which deals with the problems of the implementation and use of new technologies.

There are several definitions of multimedia tool, we will give some of them. In particular, multimedia - (English-Greek multimedia-media) is a technology that covers various means of information transmission, which includes certain programs and tools. Computers with multimedia usually have a powerful video system, the ability to view video recorders and video cameras, the ability to capture images and work with various forms of information such as color graphics, sound output, and synthesized music.³

² Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan - February 2, 2022. No. PQ-112. "On additional measures for the development of the sphere of culture and art"

³ Hasanboev.J, Torakulov X, Haydarov.M, Hasanboeva.O, Usmanov. N Explanatory dictionary from the science of pedagogy, T.: Science and technology. 2009. Page 348

The term "multimedia" is derived from the English language, "multi" means many, and "media" means environment. That is, to describe information using several environments that can be perceived by the human mind.

Multimedia is the interconnection of video and audio information controlled by interactive software with the help of modern technical and software tools, combining text, sound, graphics, photos and video. In this case, information can be available on various information carriers - magnetic and optical discs, audio and video tapes. (photo 1)

1-photo

Multimedia – is a modern information technology that allows the integration of text, sound, video and various animations in a computer system

Multimedia technology is a technology that envisages the delivery of educational materials to students on the basis of data in the form of audio, video, text, graphics and animation (movement of objects in space) based on the software and technical tools of informatics. If we look at the definition of the concept of technology, when translated from the Greek language, "techne" - (art, skill, craft, dexterity) is a set of methods of processing, production, changing the state, characteristics, form of an object. it comes in the moans. In the explanatory dictionary, this term is defined as a set of techniques used in any business, craft.

Thus, the concept of multimedia technology should be understood as modern computer information technologies that allow combining text, sound, video, graphics, animation and interactivity in a computer system.

Multimedia tools include audio speakers, microphones, video projectors, web cameras, TV tuners, CDs, interactive whiteboards, etc. (photo.2).

2 photo

Multimedia products can include e-books, textbooks, slides, karaoke, and various animations. From a pedagogical point of view, multimedia tools are a new computer-based approach to the process of education of primary school students. Computer technologies are used as an important tool in increasing the activity of students, increasing the volume of studied educational materials, and increasing the level of efficiency of the educational process. It serves to acquire knowledge, form computer literacy, and increase educational efficiency using the materials displayed on the screen by looking at the computer monitor. In multimedia computer technology, it is considered as an educational resource in addition to visual aids. Because the materials to be studied are stored in the computer memory in advance. The teacher calls up the necessary information on the monitor screen and introduces the students to the displayed materials. Based on this, they study the materials presented on the topic. In this way, students develop sufficient computer skills. At the same time, in the process of using a computer, students of school age develop their thinking, their interest in learning increases, and their worldview expands. The effectiveness of multimedia technology in the educational process can be expressed in the following form.

3-photo

Computerized education based on multimedia technology cannot replace a person, that is, a teacher. The role of the teacher is certainly important and in the first place in the existing information and education. This includes independent and creative thinking, information filling and improvement.

The text in multimedia will be short, concise, clear and understandable. A student of junior school age will not only be able to read it, but also memorize it quickly. Writing texts in different fonts and colors will attract the reader's attention.

Sound - where the information consists of different sounds, it develops emotional cognition skills in the student. Low-pitched voice, intonation, excitement are important. The live action monitor consists of the actions of various things, objects, human or animal images. Graphic images are created to visualize the subject of a particular topic under discussion. It helps to strengthen the memory, to remember the subject depending on the image of a certain object. On the basis of the above, conclusions are made between the teacher and the student through a free, live dialogue and the lesson is completed. The following can be indicated as the essence of using multimedia technologies:

the use of audio textbooks in the study of musical literature and music using multimedia technologies is focused on saving time and significantly increasing the effectiveness of teaching; new information technology tools serve as a means of teaching and educating students, developing their creative and communicative abilities, and developing computer literacy and the culture of receiving information.

the use of multimedia tools in the educational process allows to create conditions for the exchange of information and experience by simultaneously monitoring the educational process of different eras and countries, the process of musical culture education.

The emergence of multimedia systems has made fundamental changes in many areas of human activity. Multimedia technology has become one of the widely used fields in education. Because information tools based on multimedia significantly increase the effectiveness of education. It was experimentally determined that during the oral presentation of the material, the student can receive and process up to 1000 pieces of traditional information per minute, and with multimedia technologies, this figure increases to 100,000 pieces.

Multimedia tools and technologies provide an opportunity to intensify the school and increase the interest of schoolchildren in learning through modern methods of audiovisual information processing.

For example:

Visualization is seeing and reviving information in the imagination;

Implementation of the obtained information;

Contamination (mixing, mixing) gathering information and creating new concepts;

Deformation means enlarging or reducing a certain linear parameter, stretching or compressing the image;

There is a multi-window view of audiovisual information on one screen, it is possible to activate any part of the screen.

demonstration real-time display of events (video).

The use of multimedia in the educational process also has its own problems, which are as follows:

development of educational materials and manuals in the form of computer programs necessary for education;

to be able to effectively use developed computer programs in the educational process.

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